

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT pH ON ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITIES OF ALOE VERA L. (IN VIVO & IN VITRO REGENERATED) WHOLE LEAF AND INNER GEL EXTRACTS

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ABSTRACT

The present study investigates the effect of varying pH on the antimicrobial activity of *Aloe vera* L. extracts derived from both *in vivo* grown and *in vitro* regenerated plants. Ethyl acetate extracts of whole leaf and inner gel were evaluated against a wide range of clinically significant microorganisms, including bacterial species such as *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, fungal species like *Aspergillus spp.*, and yeasts including *Candida albicans*. The extracts were adjusted to different pH levels (3.0, 6.0, and 9.0) to assess their stability and efficacy under varying acidic and alkaline conditions. Antimicrobial activity was determined using the disc diffusion method, and results were statistically analysed using ANOVA. The findings revealed that the antimicrobial activity of *Aloe vera* L. extracts was significantly influenced by pH. Maximum inhibitory effects were observed under acidic conditions (pH 3.0), where the activity was

slightly higher than the control. At neutral pH (6.0), a marginal reduction in antimicrobial activity was noted, whereas at alkaline pH (9.0), a significant decline in inhibitory effects was observed across most tested microorganisms. Importantly, control solutions adjusted to similar pH levels did not exhibit antimicrobial activity, confirming that the observed effects

were due to the plant extracts rather than pH alone. The results suggest that the bioactive compounds in *Aloe vera* L. are more stable and effective in acidic environments, possibly due to their cationic nature, which enhances interaction with negatively charged microbial cell surfaces. This study highlights the potential application of *Aloe vera* L. extracts as natural antimicrobial agents, particularly in acidic conditions, and supports their use in pharmaceutical and food preservation industries.

KEYWORDS: *Aloe vera* L., Antimicrobial activity, pH-dependent stability, Phytochemical extracts and Pathogenic microorganisms.

INTRODUCTION

In present investigation, number of pathogens of clinical significance including bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus cereus*), fungi (*Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Penicillium digitatum*) and yeast (*Candida albicans*, *Candida utilis*) were tested against the ethyl acetate extracts of *Aloe vera* L. (both *in vivo* grown and *in vitro* regenerated) whole leaf and inner gel at different pH to test the stability of *Aloe vera* L. extracts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of crude extract

Leaves of the *Aloe vera* L. were collected from the already *in vitro* propagated and properly acclimatized 9-12 months old plants. *In vitro* propagation was the previous phase of our study to produce quality plant material to meet industrial requirement. Simultaneously leaves from 9-12 months old *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. plants were also collected. Freshly collected *Aloe vera* L. leaves were washed with distilled water, followed by disinfecting with ethanol 70%. Later, in case of whole leaf crude extract preparation, leaves were chopped into the small pieces and were exposed to 50°C for 3 days to get dried. After complete drying, leaf parts were powdered using electric grinder, simultaneously in case of only gel crude extract preparation, upper green skin/rind of leaves was removed and latex was cut into small pieces and both types of leaf materials were homogenized separately. The homogenized materials were extracted with ethanol (95%). The ethanol from the extracted leaf materials was evaporated at 65°C temperature in water bath. The solvent was completely removed and dried to get powder. All the powdered plant materials including whole leaf and only gel were used for the preparation of aqueous and solvent extracts.

Aqueous extract

Extracts were prepared using the modified method of Case.^[1] 1:3 (w/v) ratios were used for the powdered leaf material and distilled water for extract preparation. The pulverized leaf material was used to prepare an infusion in hot (95°C) distilled water. The infusion was left overnight under refrigeration (4°C) to prevent any possible contamination. After 24 h the extracts were kept in rotary shaker at 100 rpm for 1 h and filtered with Whatman No.1 filter paper and subsequently subjected to lyophilization at – 47.5°C. The frozen extract was then freeze dried to a powder, weighed, transferred into separate vial and preserved at 4°C for future analysis.

Solvent extracts

As in case of aqueous extract here also 1:3 (w/v) ratios were used for the powdered leaf material and different solvents for extract preparation. The pulverized leaves material was mixed with sufficient quantity of solvent that is ethyl acetate. It was kept in rotary shaker at 100 rpm overnight and filtered with Whatman No.1 filter paper and subsequently subjected to lyophilization at – 47.5°C. The dried extract thus obtained was weighed, transferred into vials and preserved at 4°C for future analysis.

The ethyl acetate extracts of *Aloe vera* L. (both *in vivo* grown and *in vitro* regenerated) whole leaf and inner gel at a concentration of 100mg/10ml were adjusted with sterile 0.1 N HCl and NaOH to have pH ranging from 3.0 to 9.0. Then pH adjusted extracts were filtered with 0.22 µm membrane and used within 60 min. Sterile distilled water adjusted to different pH as above was used as an acid/alkali control solution to ascertain whether observed change in bacterial growth was because of acidic/alkaline pH or because of extracts. pH-unadjusted extracts were used as controls. Antimicrobial activity of pH adjusted and control samples were evaluated by disc diffusion method. Experiments were performed in triplicates.

Statistical analysis

All the analysis were carried out in triplicates and expressed as mean ± SD. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) were performed using the one-way analysis of variance. Significant differences between means were determined by Duncan's multiple range tests. P values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The effects of pH on antimicrobial activity of ethyl acetate extract of *in vivo* and *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf and only gel are represented in Table 1 – 4. It was found that at pH 3.0, the inhibitory activity of ethyl acetate extracts were slightly higher than that of control. At pH 6.0, the antibacterial activity seemed to slightly lower than that of control extract. Whereas at pH 9.0, inhibitory effects were significantly lower than that of control extract.

Therefore, the extracts tested having an excellent antimicrobial activity when pH was maintained around 3.0 – 6.0 and tended to lose their antimicrobial effects when the pH was increased towards alkaline side. At the same time acid and alkali control solutions were not showing their inhibitory actions against any of the microorganism tested. So that a significant drop in the inhibitory activity of the extracts was depicted with the increase in pH toward alkaline side while antimicrobial actions was found excellent at acidic pH.

It has been reported that antimicrobial compound appeared to be stabilized in cationic forms that may interact with and interrupt negatively charged bacterial cells.^[2] Consequently, dependence of antibacterial activity of *Aloe vera* L. extracts on low pH recommends that the molecular structure or charge of bacterial species may be the key component for its inhibitory actions.

The acid stability of plant extracts are critical aspects of their use in food processing applications as natural preservatives to control microbial growth.

Table 1: Effect of pH of ethyl acetate extract of *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf on inhibitory zone (mm) against pathogenic organisms.

S.No.	Microorganisms (Pathogens)	Control	pH		
			3.0	6.0	9.0
1	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	21.49 ± 1.87*	22.83 ± 0.20	20.24 ± 0.36	14.57 ± 0.04
2	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	NT	NT	NT	NT
3	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	16.20 ± 0.06	16.08 ± 0.72	15.72 ± 2.19	11.23 ± 0.26
4	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	17.54 ± 1.46	18.14 ± 0.28	16.48 ± 1.29	12.20 ± 0.63
5	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	15.62 ± 0.08	16.06 ± 1.24	13.24 ± 0.58	09.82 0.33
6	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	16.02 ± 0.86	17.76 ± 0.57	14.39 ± 1.04	10.19 ± 0.31
7	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	14.87 ± 0.16	15.34 ± 0.20	13.57 ± 0.18	10.62 ± 0.04
8	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	21.34 ± 1.49	21.73 ± 1.26	20.42 ± 0.39	13.50 ± 1.74
9	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	17.54 ± 0.90	17.38 ± 0.57	16.04 ± 1.83	11.12 ± 1.37
10	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	14.23 ± 0.52	14.19 ± 0.04	13.25 ± 1.60	09.29 ± 0.24
11	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	17.04 ± 0.62	17.50 ± 0.92	16.62 ± 0.04	09.20 ± 0.83
12	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	14.48 ± 1.19	14.31 ± 1.18	13.08 ± 0.86	08.57 ± 0.47
13	<i>Penicillium digitatum</i>	16.33 ± 0.36	17.06 ± 0.42	15.16 ± 0.72	10.82 ± 1.20
14	<i>Candida albicans</i>	19.24 ± 0.02	19.58 ± 1.63	17.30 ± 0.21	12.35 ± 0.91
15	<i>Candida utilis</i>	17.68 ± 0.42	17.20 ± 0.58	16.64 ± 1.26	11.21 ± 0.40

The values are given as Mean ± SD of triplicates

The concentration of extracts used was 100 µg/disc

* Inhibitory zone in mm, including diameter of disc (5.0 mm)

Table 2: Effect of pH of ethyl acetate extract of *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. only gel on inhibitory zone (mm) against pathogenic organisms.

S.No.	Microorganisms (Pathogens)	Control	pH		
			3.0	6.0	9.0
1	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	25.40 ± 1.54*	25.87 ± 0.56	24.18 ± 0.24	13.21 ± 0.36
2	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	NT	NT	NT	NT
3	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	19.36 ± 0.93	19.24 ± 1.40	17.82 ± 0.54	10.37 ± 1.42
4	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	21.43 ± 0.82	22.20 ± 0.26	20.92 ± 0.37	12.83 ± 1.21
5	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	19.33 ± 0.36	19.20 ± 0.27	18.64 ± 1.51	11.26 ± 0.30
6	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	20.25 ± 0.83	21.39 ± 0.63	19.36 ± 0.08	12.74 ± 0.83
7	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	18.72 ± 1.20	18.71 ± 0.24	17.36 ± 0.18	12.82 ± 0.71
8	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	25.32 ± 0.52	26.18 ± 0.63	24.47 ± 1.84	15.29 ± 0.27
9	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	22.25 ± 0.63	23.08 ± 1.41	21.39 ± 0.46	14.20 ± 0.51
10	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	19.57 ± 1.57	19.37 ± 0.25	17.26 ± 1.37	11.17 ± 0.04
11	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	23.48 ± 0.83	23.30 ± 1.19	22.39 ± 1.24	14.58 ± 0.20
12	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	18.33 ± 0.02	18.82 ± 0.36	16.82 ± 0.72	10.81 ± 1.43
13	<i>Penicillium digitatum</i>	22.20 ± 0.12	22.57 ± 0.80	21.87 ± 0.57	13.76 ± 1.32
14	<i>Candida albicans</i>	25.65 ± 0.18	26.42 ± 0.47	24.03 ± 1.20	16.19 ± 0.81
15	<i>Candida utilis</i>	24.43 ± 0.10	24.17 ± 1.22	23.60 ± 0.34	15.24 ± 0.62

The values are given as Mean ± SD of triplicates

The concentration of extracts used was 100 µg/disc

* Inhibitory zone in mm, including diameter of disc (5.0 mm).

Table 3: Effect of pH of ethyl acetate extract of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf on inhibitory zone (mm) against pathogenic organisms.

S.No.	Microorganisms (Pathogens)	Control	pH		
			3.0	6.0	9.0
1	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	18.15 ± 0.05*	18.73 ± 0.57	17.36 ± 1.18	14.39 ± 0.24
2	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	NT	NT	NT	NT
3	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	13.24 ± 1.35	13.38 ± 0.26	12.83 ± 0.42	09.24 ± 0.52
4	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	15.62 ± 0.30	16.10 ± 0.05	14.06 ± 0.27	10.47 ± 0.39
5	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	12.31 ± 0.52	12.47 ± 0.19	11.24 ± 0.20	08.76 ± 1.18
6	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	12.57 ± 0.60	13.02 ± 0.83	12.36 ± 0.51	09.43 ± 0.26
7	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	10.39 ± 0.56	11.64 ± 0.40	10.76 ± 0.24	08.68 ± 0.82
8	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	18.62 ± 0.36	18.62 ± 0.25	17.54 ± 0.09	12.30 ± 1.33
9	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	14.54 ± 1.06	15.53 ± 0.36	13.72 ± 0.26	09.26 ± 0.57
10	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	11.86 ± 0.08	12.20 ± 1.82	11.24 ± 0.19	08.24 ± 1.76
11	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	14.28 ± 0.20	15.46 ± 1.26	13.57 ± 0.21	08.50 ± 0.35
12	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	12.50 ± 0.05	13.35 ± 0.29	12.18 ± 0.50	08.74 ± 0.14
13	<i>Penicillium digitatum</i>	13.53 ± 0.84	13.71 ± 0.37	12.29 ± 1.72	09.36 ± 0.58
14	<i>Candida albicans</i>	17.08 ± 0.47	17.06 ± 0.24	16 ± 96 ± 0.28	10.21 ± 0.30
15	<i>Candida utilis</i>	15.54 ± 0.05	16.21 ± 1.63	14.60 ± 0.37	09.32 ± 0.63

The values are given as Mean ± SD of triplicates

The concentration of extracts used was 100 µg/disc

* Inhibitory zone in mm, including diameter of disc (5.0 mm).

Table 4: Effect of pH of ethyl acetate extract of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. only gel on inhibitory zone (mm) against pathogenic organisms.

S.No.	Microorganisms (Pathogens)	Control	pH		
			3.0	6.0	9.0
1	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	20.65 ± 0.28*	21.38 ± 0.63	19.21 ± 0.76	13.82 ± 0.19
2	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	NT	NT	NT	NT
3	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	14.36 ± 0.33	14.91 ± 0.73	13.62 ± 1.49	09.28 ± 0.57
4	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	16.55 ± 0.82	17.48 ± 1.54	15.86 ± 1.36	10.42 ± 0.50
5	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	14.62 ± 0.12	14.60 ± 0.27	13.37 ± 0.04	09.03 ± 0.26
6	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	13.43 ± 0.39	13.23 ± 0.82	12.87 ± 0.18	08.46 ± 1.37
7	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	12.57 ± 0.52	12.64 ± 0.48	11.56 ± 0.62	08.27 ± 0.81
8	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	20.33 ± 0.72	21.29 ± 0.87	19.17 ± 0.28	14.30 ± 0.20
9	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	15.85 ± 0.22	16.40 ± 0.63	14.26 ± 0.19	09.62 ± 1.76
10	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	12.26 ± 0.36	13.74 ± 0.55	11.48 ± 1.83	08.41 ± 0.35
11	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	16.31 ± 0.70	17.41 ± 0.74	14.69 ± 0.24	08.37 ± 0.04
12	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	13.57 ± 0.21	14.54 ± 0.19	13.42 ± 0.21	09.29 ± 0.63
13	<i>Penicillium digitatum</i>	15.39 ± 0.15	15.28 ± 1.57	14.39 ± 0.70	10.15 ± 0.60
14	<i>Candida albicans</i>	18.04 ± 0.42	18.38 ± 0.26	17.63 ± 0.25	11.71 ± 0.37
15	<i>Candida utilis</i>	16.48 ± 0.62	16.12 ± 0.29	15.30 ± 1.42	10.18 ± 0.83

The values are given as Mean ± SD of triplicates

The concentration of extracts used was 100 µg/disc

* Inhibitory zone in mm, including diameter of disc (5.0 mm)

DISCUSSION

The acid tolerance of plant extracts is the critical aspects of their use in food processing applications as an important property for compound to be used in food preservation or can extend the expiry of the product. Consuming healthy, nutritious and contamination free food are the important necessary aspects in terms of human health.

So that in the current study the stability of the *Aloe vera* L. extracts under various pH conditions were assessed. Ethyl acetate extracts of *in vitro* and *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. were assessed for its acid stability. It was found that ethyl acetate extracts were showed the significant pH stability.

Similar results were found by many other workers who tested the effects of pH on different spices and herbs. Srinivasan *et al.* were examined the antibacterial activity and stability of garlic extract at different pH and found the similar results.^[3]

Several other workers such as Bakhshayeshi *et al.*, Mahmoud *et al.*, Ruenroengklin *et al.*, Jenshi roobha *et al.*, Devi *et al.*, Dehghan *et al.*, Abu-Gharbia *et al.*, Anees *et al.*, Rakkimuthu *et al.*, were also assessed the pH stability of various herbal extracts for their antimicrobial activities against several pathogens of human health significance and found the similar results which strongly supports our current study.^[4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12]

CONCLUSION

In current study the stability of ethyl acetate extract of the *Aloe vera* L. under various pH conditions were assessed. It was found that ethyl acetate extracts were showed the significant pH stability. Therefore, in view of these results, the ability of the extracts to inhibit the growth of several bacterial and fungal species is an indication of the broad-spectrum antimicrobial potential of *Aloe vera* L. which makes the plant a candidate for bio-prospecting for antimicrobial drugs.

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